

The Effect of Probiotic Yogurt Consumption on Salivary pH in Active Smokers

Poetry Oktanauli¹, Pinka Taher², Rini Triani³, Andy Hidayat⁴, Herlia Nur Istindiah⁵, Mirna Febriani⁶, Ratih Widyastuti⁷, Giska Widadhiya Fakhira⁸

^{1,2,4}Department of Oral Biology, Faculty of Dentistry, Prof. Dr. Moestopo (Beragama) University, Jakarta

³Department of Paedodontics, Faculty of Dentistry, Prof. Dr. Moestopo (Beragama) University, Jakarta

⁵Department of Orthodontics, Faculty of Dentistry, Prof. Dr. Moestopo (Beragama) University, Jakarta

⁶Department of Dental Materials and Technology, Faculty of Dentistry, Prof. Dr. Moestopo (Beragama) University, Jakarta

⁷Department of Periodontics, Faculty of Dentistry, Prof. Dr. Moestopo (Beragama) University, Jakarta

⁸Faculty of Dentistry, Prof. Dr. Moestopo (Beragama) University, Jakarta

ABSTRACT

Backgrounds: One of the efforts to maintain salivary pH balance is through the consumption of probiotics. Probiotic yogurt contains various nutrients and beneficial bacteria that can increase salivary pH. Active smokers tend to have a lower salivary pH, which increases the risk of dental caries. Consuming probiotic yogurt may help neutralize oral acidity in smokers and support oral health.

Objectives: This research aims to examine the effect of consuming probiotic yogurt on the salivary pH of active smokers.

Methods: This research employed a clinical experimental design using a pretest-posttest with control group approach. Data normality was tested using the Shapiro-Wilk test, while statistical analysis was conducted using the Paired Sample T-Test followed by the Independent T-Test.

Results: The statistical test showed a significant increase in the salivary pH of active smokers ($P = 0.000$) after consuming probiotic yogurt.

Conclusion: Consuming probiotic yogurt can effectively increase the salivary pH of active smokers.

KEYWORDS: Salivary pH, Probiotic Yogurt, Active Smokers, Oral Health.

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
23 September 2025

Available on:
<https://ijpbms.com/>

INTRODUCTION

Saliva is a complex fluid and plays an important role in maintaining the balance of the oral cavity ecosystem, which comes from the secretions of the major and minor salivary glands. 1 The phosphate and calcium content in saliva plays an important role in the process of tooth remineralization. 2 Saliva has various functions, including lubricating tissues in the oral cavity, protecting against dehydration, and acting as a buffer system that helps neutralize the acidic pH of saliva. This is important to prevent the demineralization process of tooth enamel.¹

Salivary potential of hydrogen (pH) is the level of acidity or alkalinity of saliva, with normal values ranging from 6.7 to 7.3.¹⁻³ Several factors can influence changes in

salivary pH, including the type of food and drink consumed, stimulation of salivary secretion, salivary flow rate, the presence of microorganisms in the oral cavity, and saliva's buffering capacity. An increase in alkaline salivary pH can trigger calculus formation, while a decrease in acidic salivary pH can cause mineral loss from the tooth structure, leading to the formation of dental caries. This is in accordance with the explanation of Sawitri et al. (2021).¹

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines a smoker as an individual who smokes tobacco products either regularly every day or only occasionally.⁴ Smoking is a common activity carried out by people, from teenagers to the elderly.⁵ The World Health Organization (WHO) in 2018 showed that Indonesia was among the ten countries with the

The Effect of Probiotic Yogurt Consumption on Salivary pH in Active Smokers

largest number of smokers and ranked 3rd in the world, after China and India. ⁶ Based on the 2023 Indonesian Health Survey (SKI), it shows that the number of smokers in Indonesia is around 70 million smokers, 24.5% or around 17 million smokers among them are smokers aged 20-24 years. The average number of cigarettes smoked per person per day is around 12 cigarettes or the equivalent of one pack of cigarettes.⁵

Smoking not only has a general effect on the body but can also potentially cause pathological disorders in the oral cavity. ⁷ Some of the impacts of smoking on dental and oral health include tooth discoloration, periodontal disease, tooth decay, and tooth loss. ⁸ Cigarettes contain nicotine, an addictive substance. Nicotine is absorbed through the mucous membranes and lungs within 10-20 seconds, then enters the bloodstream and is distributed to the brain and all body tissues. Nicotine in the blood affects the blood vessels in the salivary glands, causing changes in the function and structure of the salivary glands, which can result in decreased salivary secretion.⁹

Saliva is secreted during resting conditions with a salivary flow rate of 20 ml per hour or about 0.33 ml/minute.⁴ Continuous exposure to cigarette smoke is one of the causes of decreased salivary flow due to atrophy of acini cells in the salivary glands.^{4,10} The long-term impact of smoking is at risk of experiencing dry mouth. Dry mouth can cause anaerobic bacteria to multiply more rapidly and cause the salivary pH of the oral cavity to become acidic. Smokers experience a decrease in salivary flow rate which can cause reduced bicarbonate secretion in saliva as a buffer capacity.¹⁰ Salivary buffer capacity is closely related to salivary pH.¹ The average salivary pH of filter smokers of 7-20 cigarettes per day is 5.55. Repeated decreases in salivary pH over a certain period of time can cause dental caries. This condition causes the tooth surface to demineralize due to the acidic environment that occurs in the oral cavity.¹¹

A decrease in salivary pH in the oral cavity of smokers can cause the oral cavity to become acidic. ¹² Saliva with an acidic degree of acidity (pH), namely between 4.5-5.5, provides conditions conducive to the growth of acidogenic bacteria such as *Streptococcus mutans* in the

mouth. One way to maintain microbial balance in the oral cavity is by consuming probiotics. ^{13,14} Probiotics contain bacteria such as *Lactobacillus* and *Bifidobacteria*, which play a role in preventing the development of pathogenic bacteria. ¹⁵ Yogurt, kefir, kumiss, Bulgarian milk, piima, taete, and skyr are examples of probiotic beverage products. However, the most commonly consumed probiotic beverage product in the community is yogurt. Yogurt is fermented sour milk and has various nutritional contents such as calcium, protein, potassium, fat, and vitamins B2 (riboflavin), B6 (pyridoxine), and B12 (cyanocobalamin). Yogurt is not erosive, has a high buffer capacity, and has low cariogenic potential. The advantages of yogurt in maintaining oral health include its ability to increase salivary pH and stimulate saliva secretion.¹⁴

Research conducted by Malavalli et al. in 2022, regarding the effect of consuming probiotic yogurt on salivary pH, showed that the average salivary pH level after consuming probiotic yogurt increased. The study also showed that salivary calcium levels increased, which is important for helping prevent dental caries by remineralizing demineralized tooth enamel.¹³ Based on the description above, the researchers wanted to further examine the effect of consuming probiotic yogurt on salivary pH in active smokers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The data obtained will be analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), beginning with a normality test using the Shapiro-Wilk test. This method was chosen because the study sample size was less than 50 ($n < 50$). The Shapiro-Wilk test aims to assess whether the data are normally distributed. The results of the normality test in this study indicate a normal distribution, as the significance value ($p > 0.05$) was found. The normally distributed data will then be subjected to parametric statistical testing, namely the Paired Sample T-Test, to determine the comparison of salivary pH before and after treatment. An Independent T-Test will then be conducted to compare the mean salivary pH before and after treatment between the control and treatment groups.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The research results can be seen in the following table:

Table 1. Frequency Distribution of Subjects by Age and Gender

Subject Characteristics	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age		
19 years old	1	6.25
20 years old	4	25.00
21 years old	9	56.25
23 years old	1	6.25
24 years old	1	6.25
Gender		

The Effect of Probiotic Yogurt Consumption on Salivary pH in Active Smokers

Male	12	75.00
Female	4	25.00
Total	16	100

Table 1 above groups the data based on age and gender with an age range of 19-24 years, this is in accordance with the research inclusion criteria, namely subjects aged 19-25 years. The data obtained shows that there is 1 man aged 19 years, 4 men aged 20 years, 6 men

and 3 women aged 21 years, 1 man aged 23 years, and 1 woman aged 24 years. The overall total of male is 12 people or 75% and female 4 people or 25%, indicating that the number of male subjects is more than female subjects, with the most age being at 21 years.

Table 2. Frequency Distribution of Saliva pH of Active Smokers Before and After Consuming Mineral Water

Variable	N	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std. Deviation
pH before control (mineral water)	16	6.51	6.87	6.7213	0.11401
pH after control (mineral water)	16	6.59	6.95	6.7900	0.11171

Based on table 2 above, it shows that the salivary pH before consuming mineral water has a minimum value of 6.51, a maximum value of 6.87, a mean value of 6.7213, and a standard deviation of 0.11401. The salivary pH value after

consuming mineral water has a minimum value of 6.59, a maximum value of 6.95, a mean value of 6.7900, and a standard deviation of 0.11171.

Table 3. Frequency Distribution of Saliva pH of Active Smokers Before and After Consuming Probiotic Yogurt

Variable	N	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std. Deviation
pH before control (yoghurt)	16	6.62	6.96	6.7675	0.10050
pH after control (yoghurt)	16	7.05	7.35	7.2250	0.08033

Based on table 3, the results of descriptive analysis show that salivary pH before consuming probiotic yogurt has a minimum value of 6.62, a maximum value of 6.96, a mean value of 6.7675, and a standard deviation of 0.10050. The

salivary pH value after consuming probiotic yogurt has a minimum value of 7.05, a maximum value of 7.35, a mean value of 7.2250, and a standard deviation of 0.08033.

Table 4. Data Normality Test

Treatment		Saphiro Wilk			Information
Group	Statistic	Df	P (Sig.)		
Mineral water	Salivary pH (before)	0.941	16	0.355	Normally Distributed Data
	Salivary pH (after)	0.955	16	0.570	Normally Distributed Data
Probiotic Yoghurt	Salivary pH (before)	0.945	16	0.416	Normally Distributed Data
	Salivary pH (after)	0.969	16	0.830	Normally Distributed Data

The data on table 4 shows that the salivary pH value before consuming mineral water is 0.355, while the salivary pH value after consuming mineral water increases to 0.570. In the treatment with probiotic yogurt, the salivary pH data before consuming probiotic yogurt is 0.416 and the salivary

pH after consuming probiotic yogurt is 0.830. The results of the four data both before and after consuming mineral water and probiotic yogurt show that the data is normally distributed because the p value (Sig.) >0.05.

Table 5. Paired Sample T-Test

	P (Sig.)
	Two-sided p
Salivary pH before and after (mineral water)	0.000
Salivary pH before and after (probiotic yoghurt)	0.000

*t-test, CI 95% p<0.05 (significant)

Based on table 5, the results of the Paired Sample T-Test show a significant difference in salivary pH values before and after consumption, both with mineral water and

probiotic yogurt treatments. In the treatment using mineral water, the salivary pH value showed a statistically significant change, with a p value (Sig.) of 0.000 (<0.05).

The Effect of Probiotic Yogurt Consumption on Salivary pH in Active Smokers

Treatment with probiotic yogurt also resulted in a significant difference between salivary pH before and after consumption, with a p value (Sig.) of 0.000 (<0.05). Thus,

it can be concluded that salivary pH increased after consuming mineral water and probiotic yogurt.

Table 6. Independent T-Test of Mineral Water and Probiotic Yogurt Treatment

		Value		
		<i>Equal variances assumed</i>	<i>Equal variances not assumed</i>	
<i>Levene's Test for Equality of Variance</i>	<i>F</i>	30.447		
	<i>Sig.</i>	0.000		
<i>t-test for Equality of Means</i>	<i>T</i>	-14.969	-14.969	
	<i>Df</i>	30	16.188	
	<i>Sig. (2-tailed)</i>	0.000	0.000	
	<i>Mean Difference</i>	-0.38875	-0.38875	
	<i>Std. Error Difference</i>	0.02597	0.02597	
	<i>95% Confidence Interval of the Difference</i>	<i>Lower</i>	-0.44179	-0.44375
		<i>Upper</i>	-0.33571	-0.33375

**t*-test, CI 95%, P<0.05

(significant difference between mineral water and probiotic yogurt treatments)

In Table 6, the results of the Independent T-Test for the control group consuming mineral water and the treatment group consuming probiotic yogurt, obtained a p-value (Sig.) of 0.000 (<0.05). Thus, it can be concluded that there is a significant difference in the increase in salivary pH between the groups consuming mineral water and probiotic yogurt.

The subjects in this study were active, light smokers, smoking 5-10 cigarettes per day. The average salivary pH of the subjects in this study was within the normal range, in contrast to the general population, which typically exhibits a lower salivary pH. This could be influenced by the duration of smoking or the number of cigarettes smoked per day, as well as the subjects being dental students who have a better understanding of maintaining oral hygiene and health.

Based on the research results, statistical tests using the Independent T-Test obtained a p-value (Sig.) of 0.000 (<0.05), indicating a more significant increase in salivary pH in those consuming probiotic yogurt compared to the group consuming mineral water. The difference in salivary pH before and after the probiotic yogurt treatment group was 0.46, while the difference in the mineral water control group was 0.07. The results of Sulastri et al.'s study entitled The Effect of Yogurt Drinks on Salivary pH of Elementary School Students in 2018 also showed an increase in salivary pH but not significant between the salivary pH of subjects consuming probiotic yogurt and those not consuming probiotic yogurt. The increase in salivary acidity (pH) in both studies occurred due to the probiotic content in it, probiotics are able to prevent the development of bacteria that cause dental caries (acidogenic bacteria) and increase salivary pH, thereby inhibiting the process of tooth demineralization.² The increase in salivary pH also occurs because the sour taste produced by the yogurt functions as a chemical stimulus that can stimulate an increase in the volume of saliva secretion. With increased salivary flow, the buffering capacity of saliva

also increases so that the salivary pH value also increases.¹⁶

In Sulastri's study, the increase in salivary pH was not significant. This was because the subjects were elementary school students aged 7-11. In elementary school-aged children, the physiological conditions and salivary gland activity differ from those of adults, so the response to consuming probiotic yogurt in increasing salivary pH tends to be lower. Furthermore, elementary school-aged children have less awareness of oral hygiene and limited knowledge about dental and oral health. In this study, conducted on active smokers who were adult students, the effect of probiotics was more pronounced due to the greater need to counteract the acidic effects of pathogenic bacteria resulting from smoking, resulting in a more statistically significant change in salivary pH. This study also involved students from the Faculty of Dentistry, who naturally have better knowledge of dental and oral health.

Another study, conducted by Srivastava et al. in 2016, showed that probiotic yogurt was more effective in increasing salivary pH than regular yogurt. The acidity (pH) of yogurt ranged from 3.7 to 4.5. Probiotic yogurt contains various ions such as potassium, calcium, sodium, and phosphorus, which can stimulate increased salivary secretion and contribute to an increase in salivary pH. Furthermore, the calcium content in yogurt plays a crucial role in tooth remineralization, and the vitamins C and D it contains can trigger chemical stimuli that increase salivary flow.^{17,18}

CONCLUSION

In this study, it can be concluded that probiotic yogurt has the ability to increase salivary pH. Consuming probiotic yogurt plays a role in maintaining dental and oral health by maintaining salivary pH within the normal range, thereby helping to prevent tooth decay. The increase in salivary acidity (pH) after consuming probiotic yogurt

The Effect of Probiotic Yogurt Consumption on Salivary pH in Active Smokers

indicates that probiotic yogurt can be used as an alternative drink that is effective in inhibiting bacterial growth in the oral cavity, as well as providing additional knowledge for the public, especially active smokers.

REFERENCES

- I. Sawitri H, Maulina N. Derajat pH Saliva pada Mahasiswa Program Studi Kedokteran Fakultas Kedokteran Universitas Malikussaleh yang Mengonsumsi Kopi Tahun 2020. *Averrous: Jurnal Kedokteran dan Kesehatan Malikussaleh*. 2021; 7(1): 84-94.
- II. Sulastri S. The Effect of Drinking Yogurt on the pH Saliva of Elementary School Students. *Jurnal Kesehatan Gigi*. 2018; 5(1): 24-29.
- III. Buktare K, Parikh S, Shah J. Comparative Evaluation of Salivary Flow Rate, pH, and Alkaline Phosphatase in Tobacco Users and Healthy Individuals: A Biomarker Study. *Journal of International Oral Health*. 2024; 16(6): 479-486.
- IV. Qalbi MZ, Iramah M. Asterina. Perbedaan Derajat Keasaman (pH) Saliva Antara Perokok dan Bukan Perokok pada Siswa SMA PGRI 1 Padang. *Jurnal Kesehatan Andalas*. 2018. 7(3): 358-363.
- V. Kemenkes. *Laporan Tematik; Survei Kesehatan Indonesia (SKI) Tahun 2023*. Jakarta: Kementerian Kesehatan Republik Indonesia; 2024: 425-427.
- VI. World Health Organization. *WHO Global Report on Trends in Prevalence of Tobacco Smoking 2000-2025*, Second Edition. Geneva. 2018.
- VII. Pinto KP, Ferreira CM, Maia LC, Sassone LM, Fidalgo TK, Silva EJ. Does Tobacco Smoking Predispose to Apical Periodontitis and Endodontic Treatment Need? A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *International Endodontic Journal*. Blackwell Publishing Ltd; 2020: 1068-83.
- VIII. Nuraisya, Setiawan MA, Zainal NA, Anzelina. Hubungan Tingkat Pengetahuan Perokok terhadap Status Kebersihan Gigi Dan Mulut Di Desa Garuda Kec.Abuki Kab.Konawe. *Jurnal Kesehatan dan Kesehatan Gigi*. 2024; 5(1): 1-5.
- IX. Ramadhani AI, Tjahajawati S, Pramesti HT. Perbedaan Volume, pH Saliva dan Kondisi Rongga Mulut Wanita Perokok dan Non Perokok. *Jurnal Kedokteran Gigi Universitas Padjadjaran*. 2022;34(2):100-108.
- X. Murniwati, Oenzil F, Kamal I, Minarni. Relationship of Smoking Habit with Acidity Degree (pH) from Civil Engineering College Student 2010 of Faculty of Engineering Andalas Univer Sity. *Cakradanya Dent J*. 2017; 9(2): 90-95.
- XI. Priyambodo RA, Nurindah. Pengaruh Mengunyah Permen Karet Xylitol terhadap pH Saliva Perokok. *Media Kesehatan Gigi*. 2018; 17(1):1-7.
- XII. Theresia TT, Asia RA, Goalbertus, Louisa M, et al. *Bahaya Karies Gigi dan Penyakit Periodontal*. Banyumas: Arta Media; 2023: 13.
- XIII. Malavalli PL, Shetty SB, Thimmaiah C, Ramlan A, Hugar SM, Meharwade P. Evaluation of the Effect of Probiotic Yogurt Consumption on Salivary pH, Buffering Capacity and Calcium Level in 6-12- year- old Children. *International Journal of Clinical Pediatric Dentistry*. 2022; 15: 195-198.
- XIV. Zebua FC, Wilvia, Nababan I, Erawati S. Pengaruh Berkumur Larutan Probiotik terhadap Peningkatan pH Saliva pada Anak-anak. *Prima Journal of Oral and Dental Sciences*. 2019;2(2):36-39.
- XV. Yuniastuti A. *Monograf Probiotik*. Semarang: Unnes Press. 2015: 3, 4, 8, 9, 11, 17, 19-22.
- XVI. Siswosubroto AE, Pangemanan DHC, Leman MA. Gambaran Konsumsi Yoghurt Terhadap Waktu Peningkatan pH Saliva. *Pharmacon*. 2015; 4(4): 2302-2493
- XVII. Rachmaputri, AF. Pengaruh Mengonsumsi Yoghurt terhadap pH saliva Anak Tunagrahita Ringan. *JDHT Journal of Dental Hygiene and Therapy*. 2024; 5(2): 110-116.
- XVIII. Srivastava S, Saha S, Kumari M, Mohd S. Effect of Probiotic Curd on Salivary pH and Streptococcus mutans: a Double Blind Parallel Randomized Controlled Trial. *Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research: JCDR*, 2016; 10(2): 13-16.